

A Study on the Structural Design and Fabrication of Composite Vehicle Door

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ABSTRACT

Composite door, which adopts a sandwich structure for improving the stiffness, soundproofness and crushworthiness, has been developed for lightweight electric vehicle. Structural analysis of stiffness and crush characteristics for the composite door was performed using the finite element method. The result of analysis shows that the composite door has a superior side impact protection performance compared to the steel door. Resin-transfer-molding process is used to fabricate the outer panel of the composite door. Resin flow analysis to determine the injection gate and ventilation ports on the set of RTM molds has been conducted. The weight savings of the composite door to a steel door are estimated to be about 35%.

INTRODUCTION

In accordance with the new environmental regulations such as CAFE, automobile manufacturers are putting more efforts on reducing the emission level and increasing the fuel economy. Among the various methods used to achieve these goals, building a vehicle with lightweight body has been attracting a growing interest[1]. Lightweight body is even more essential requirement for the next generation vehicles, such as electric and hybrid vehicles. There are a number of potential materials to replace steel with functional and economic benefits for both the consumer and the manufacturer. The fiber reinforced plastic composite materials are gaining popularity in the automotive industry due to better manufacturability, styling enhancements, improved corrosion and dent resistance as well as weight reduction they afford. The major uses of composite materials have been extended from the secondary structural applications i.e., body skin, hoods and trunk lid, to the load bearing structures such as frame rails, floor pans and side members.

In this study, the door, being one of the most important primary structures, is chosen as a part of vehicle to be replaced by light material. Beginning from the styling and concept design, prototype building was successfully done through the structural and forming analysis. The design process is described in Fig. 1. For a reference, there was also a development of magnesium/aluminum door that showed possibilities of the cost and weight savings compared to steel door.[2]

The composite door consists of two pieces, outer and inner panels, for carrying the load and packaging the internal components, respectively. In this paper, the design and fabrication process of outer panel will be described from a structural point of view. A sandwich type structure is adopted for the outer panel with multiaxial knitted glass fabric and polyurethane

Fig. 1 Design process of composite door

in various configurations from unidirectional to multiaxial in preferred directions to form a multilayered fabric; 2) The multilayered fabric can be combined with CSM on both sides; 3) The drapeability can be adjusted by varying the knitting configuration and the yarn/roving selection; and 4) Resin transfer molding, vacuum injection and pultrusion can be used as the suitable forming processes in addition to hand lay up and vacuum bagging.

The preliminary design parameters such as thickness and configurations of composite skin panel and foam core were decided from the results of stiffness analysis. Also, crush analysis of composite door was conducted according to the requirement of side door strength by FMVSS 214 regulation. The results of finite element analysis show that the designs of composite door in this study meet the crush strength targets. Resin-transfer-molding process is adopted to fabricate the outer panel of composite door. Unsaturated polyester is used for resin system. Flow analysis is performed to investigate proper numbers, size and locations of injection gates and ventilation ports of the RTM mold. The composite door assembly weighs 12 kg, of which 8.5 kg is due to the outer panel, and the remaining 3.5 kg is due to the inner panel. This represents about 35% weight savings compared to steel door.

CONCEPT DESIGN

The development of lightweight composite door is a part of Electric Vehicle (EV) program, which Korea Automotive Technology Institute (KATECH) manages as a government project with two automobile companies. As this Electric Vehicle program adopts a new concept different from a just converted EV based on the current mass produced internal combustion engine cars, more spacious and lighter structures are an essential consideration to compensate for heavy and voluminous batteries. This EV is supposed to be produced in small volume because of uncertain market size at this moment. Simple and cost effective way of incorporating the above essential considerations should be found at the

Fig. 2 Schematic drawing of Electric Vehicle under development by KATECH

Fig. 3 Schematic layout of composite door outer panel

conceptual design stage. To meet these goals, the EV is designed to be consisted of aluminum space frame with six-piece all composite material bodies as shown in Fig. 2 schematically. The composite door is one of these six body pieces, which makes use of foam core and multilayered fabric as raw materials for sandwich structure. The door is also designed to be a no window frame for easy manufacturing with aluminum insert for hinge part. Fig. 3 describes the preliminary design of composite door.

Finally, this composite door is expected to be of almost the same strength and stiffness as the steel door with at least 30% in weight reduction.

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

For the preliminary design of composite door, structural analysis was performed at the beginning stage of development. Also second stage of structural analysis was carried for verifying the load carrying capacity of the composite door with the design of details included. The mechanical properties of multiaxial fabric laminates, PU foams and composite sandwich plates were obtained through the standard tests. In addition, their deformation was modeled based on classical laminate theory and finite element method. Overall performance of composite door has been evaluated by its bending and torsional stiffnesses and crush behavior. For numerical analysis, I-DEAS™ and PAM-CRASH™ finite element programs were used. The finite element model of composite door is shown in Fig. 4.

No. of brick element: 144 No. of shell element: 467 	Material: PU foam Element: brick 	Material: laminate [A] Element: shell (t=2.05 mm) 	Material: laminate [B/A] Element: shell (t=4.09 mm)
Material: laminate [A/B/A] Element: shell (t=6.14 mm) 	Material: laminate [A/B/A] Element: shell (t=7.09 mm) 	Material: laminate [A/A] Element: shell (t=5.05 mm) 	Material: laminate [B] Element: shell (t=2.04 mm)

$$[A] = [0/45.1057/90.332/-45.1057]_s, [B] = [0/45.1057/90.021/-45.1057]_s$$

$$[A/B/A] = [0/45.1057/90.332/-45.1057/0/45.1057/90.332/-45.1057/0/45.1057/90.021/-45.1057]_s$$

* Al: Aluminum (Al 5025)

Fig. 4 Finite element model of composite door

MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

In order to supply the basic mechanical properties of skin panel and foam core, tensile and compressive tests according to the standard methods were performed respectively. Sandwich specimen was also fabricated for three-point bending test. From the bending tests with three different orientations of skin panels, crush behavior of sandwich structures was obtained. Two analytical methods, classical laminate theory and finite element analysis, were used to insure the appropriateness of sandwich structures modeling.

Knitted fabric laminates

Two kinds of laminated plates corresponding to upper and lower skin panels were made by RTM using multiaxial knitted fabrics. Both upper and lower laminates consist of eight layers and each layer has different mass fraction as follows:

Upper panel; [0/45/90/-45]_s: [1/1.057/0.332/1.057]_s
 Lower panel; [0/45/90/-45]_s: [1/1.057/0.021/1.057]_s

The 90 degree layers have relatively small mass fractions in both laminates. Especially, its purpose is to prevent the dispersion of 0 and 45 degree fibers in the lower panel. Table 1 shows the elastic properties of these two laminates for three tensile directions. The results from both experiments and classical laminate theory show good agreements. Fracture properties, such as strengths and fracture strains, of these two laminates from the test and finite element analysis are presented in Table 2. The properties of glass fiber and polyester matrix used in analysis are:

	Glass fiber	Polyester matrix
Elastic modulus(GPa)	73	4
Poisson's ratio	0.20	0.33
Tensile fracture strain(%)	3.3	0.4
Compressive fracture strain(%)	0.9	1.4

In the finite element analysis for the strength and fracture strain of laminate, progressive failure model into which the successive failure of each layer is taken accounted is adopted.

Table 1 Elastic properties of knitted fabric laminates

Table 2 Fracture properties of knitted fabric laminates

Load direc. (deg.)	Elastic const.	Upper laminate			Lower laminate		
		Exp	CLT	Err (%)	Exp	CLT	Err (%)
0	E _L (GPa)	14.02	13.59	3.1	14.45	15.08	4.4
	ν _{LT}	0.42	0.44	3.9	0.56	0.55	2.2
90	E _T (GPa)	10.49	9.93	5.4	8.45	8.80	4.1
	ν _{TL}	0.33	0.32	3.4	0.33	0.32	3.2
45	E(GPa)	14.64	13.76	6.0	15.14	15.20	0.4
	ν	0.19	0.24	27.5	0.22	0.18	16.1

Exp: Experiments CLT: Classical Laminate Theory

Load direc. (deg.)	Fracture const.	Upper laminate			Lower laminate		
		Exp	FEA	Err (%)	Exp	FEA	Err (%)
0	σ _c (MPa)	250.0	246.0	1.6	288.4	245.0	15.0
	ε _o (%)	2.56	2.95	15.0	2.81	2.80	0.40
90	σ _c (MPa)	126.5	110.0	13.0	67.7	74.0	9.30
	ε _o (%)	2.06	2.10	1.9	2.00	2.05	2.50
45	σ _c (MPa)	281.5	248.0	11.9	252.1	230.0	8.80
	ε _o (%)	2.61	2.75	5.40	2.51	2.40	4.40

Exp: Experiments FEA: Finite Element Analysis
 σ_c: Strength ε_o: Fracture strain

Polyurethane foam

The mechanical properties of polyurethane foam are typically characterized by compressive stiffness and strength which depend on the density and strain rate of the foams. In this study, static compression tests according to the ASTM D1621-73[4], were performed on the 0.09 g/cm³

PU foams. Also, the behaviors of foams were modeled for the finite element analysis as follows:

- 1) highly compressible elastic foam material with hysteresis response to cyclic loading.
- 2) response of the foam is directionally uncoupled.
- 3) tensile response is limited by a specified tensile strength.
- 4) compressive response follows a piecewise linear loading curve obtained from the tests.

Fig. 5 shows the stress-strain relationships of PU foam from the compression test and finite element analysis. The deformed configurations of PU foam at three different strains are also presented in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 The stress-strain relationship and deformed configurations of PU foam.

Fig. 6 Typical load-deflection curve from three point bending test of composite sandwich plate

Sandwich specimen

With laminated skin panel and foam core, 305x305 mm sandwich plates are made by RTM. These sandwich plates are cut into the specimen for three-point bending test as shown in Fig. 6. Typical load-deflection curve from three-point bending test in Fig. 6 can be divided into the two regions, i.e. a linear region that is limited to initial straight line and a nonlinear region that begins after the yield point. From the result of three-point bending test of composite sandwich plates, the following were observed:

- 1) after the yield point, excessive local deformation occurs at the loading point.
- 2) load carrying capacity of the sandwich plate is abruptly reduced after the yield point, and the fracture is induced by upper skin failure.
- 3) no cracks in the foam core, no failures of lower skin panel, and no delaminations between skin panel and core are found during the test.

Fig. 7 Sandwich finite element

To analyze the crush behavior of composite sandwich plate, finite element modeling[5,6] was used. As shown in Fig. 7, four node layered shell and eight node brick elements were used for skin panel and foam core, respectively.[7] The comparisons of load versus deflection curves between test and analysis are in Fig. 8. The overall crush behaviors of composite sandwich plate between test and FE analysis are very similar.

Fig. 8 Comparisons of load vs. deflection curves between test and finite element analysis for three point bending of composite sandwich plate

STIFFNESS ANALYSIS

The analysis considered five load cases to assess door performance. The load cases were based upon standard test procedures for door stiffness evaluation. Table 3 describes these procedures. The deflections predicted for composite door in Fig. 9 indicate that the door is expected to meet the stiffness targets for five loading cases.

Fig. 9 Summary of stiffness analysis of composite door

Table 3 Procedures for door stiffness analysis

	Supports	Load	Target
Vertical rigidity	At the hinges	900N downward load at the latch	Maximum vertical deflection of 11mm
Torsional rigidity (upper corner)	At the hinges and y, z directions at the latch	900N outboard load at the top right corner of inner edge	Maximum lateral deflection of 10mm
Torsional rigidity (lower corner)	At the hinges and y, z directions at the latch	900N outboard load at the bottom right corner of inner edge	Maximum lateral deflection of 10mm
Waist rail rigidity (inner)	At the hinges and at the latch	540N outboard distributed load at the center region of inner top edge	Maximum lateral deflection of 3mm
Waist rail rigidity (outer)	At the hinges and at the latch	540N inboard distributed load at the center region of inner top edge	Maximum lateral deflection of 7mm

CRUSH ANALYSIS

The finite element model was loaded by a moving rigid impactor into the door outer panel at a constant velocity. The schematic drawing for this set up is shown in Fig. 10. According to the side impact protection regulation(FMVSS 214 side door strength requirement), door should have minimum reactive forces at three points of the intrusion as follows;

- At initial intrusion (152.4mm): 10kN
- At intermediate intrusion (305mm): 15.6kN
- At maximum intrusion (457mm): 31.2kN

Quasistatic crush analysis was performed up to 152 mm of side impact intrusion. Under normal circumstances, the results of first 152 mm provide a good indication of whether the system will meet the full requirement. In the finite element analysis, the door was constrained at the hinges to allow normal rotation about the latch mechanism. Nonlinear springs are distributed around the door model to represents the support of the door seal. The deformed configurations and force versus deflection curve of composite door due to the side intrusion loading are shown in Fig. 11. The reactive force of composite door is well above the FMVSS 214 requirement of side door strength.

Fig. 10 Schematic drawing of side door impactor

Fig. 11 Force vs. deflection curve and deformed configurations of composite door

FLOW ANALYSIS

The resin flow analysis to determine the injection gate and ventilation ports on the set of RTM molds is conducted on the composite door. The analysis program, developed by Seoul National University using C++ language and control volume finite element method for PC version, which is owned by Samsung Heavy Industries Co., has several distinguishing features, such as predict resin flow front and pressure distribution, redefine injection gates on ventilation ports and display the results at the various stage of problem solving. This program also allows inclusion of the orthotropic permeability properties of fiber preforms but restricted to the semi-3D configuration problems including sandwich shell structures which neglect the effects of the thickness properties. Fig. 12 shows the results of flow analysis on the preliminary design of composite door which uses knitted fabric laminates and sandwich structures. The number of three node elements used in this model was 682. Even though the knitted fabric preform has orthotropic permeability, these were assumed to be isotropic since fan gate system was adopted for resin injection mold. The injection pressure in this analysis was set to the 2×10^5 Pa, and the permeability of fiber preform was 1.0×10^{-8} m² and that of fan gate was 5.0×10^{-8} m². The resin viscosity was 0.25 Pa·s and fiber volume fraction was determined to be 36%. The injected resin filled the fan gate area first, which was located at the bottom line of composite door and had much higher permeability compared to the composite door preform area, and then flow front

Fig. 12 Prediction of resin flow front during RTM process of composite door

moved parallel to the initial shape of resin flow front. The air in the fiber preform was forced to move out of the mold and the last resin-filled area, two corners of the upper region, was selected to be ventilation ports.

PROTOTYPE BUILD

The outer panel of composite door was resin-transfer-molded using fiber reinforced plastic molds. The resin system used in this process was unsaturated polyester of 0.25 Pa·s viscosity at room temperature, manufactured by KOREA Chemicals Co. (Orester R3892B), and E-glass knitted fabric is provided by Shinshin Co. in Korea. The aluminum inserts were made from 3

mm thick Al 5025 plates by bending and welding process, and polyurethane foam cores were machined from solid blocks of 0.09 g/cm³. The pressure of approximately 2×10^5 Pa was applied for resin injection process and the time required to fill the molds was about 5 minutes. The molded part was cured for 30 minutes in the mold after injection. The weight of outer panel of composite door is approximately 8.5 kg and Fig. 13 shows the molded composite door outer skin.

Fig. 13 Resin transfer molded outer panel of composite door

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a sandwich type composite door was successfully developed. The composite door was found to be effective in reducing weight while meeting all current structural performance criteria. Furthermore, the crushworthiness analysis using finite element method shows that the composite door has superior characteristics in occupant protection from the side impact to the steel door. The crushworthiness of composite door is expected to undergo experimental verification in the near future through the standard FMVSS 214 test. To utilize the composite door for mass production vehicle, surface finishes, edge trimmings, production rates, and other aspects need to be more carefully investigated as well.

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